

COMPARATIVE TANGENTIAL STRESS ANALYSES OF CURVED BEAMS

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Abstract

Many researchers have attempted to find the solution to a curved beam under load. However, the stress values arrived at failed to satisfy the boundary conditions. Curved beams find critical practical applications in chain links, crane hooks, pipe bends, and curved segments of machine tool frames. Accurate determination of stresses in curved beams is essential in preventing catastrophic failure, leading to loss and reduced life of properties. In this current study, the authors used three methods: 1) advanced computational tools to compare the strength of materials (SOM), elasticity analysis (EA), and finite element analysis (FEA) of the curved beam tangential stress of various sections. The SOM analysis was performed first, in which three cross-sections were considered: rectangular, square, and circular. All cross-sections showed similar inner and outer tangential stress ratios. Next came the EA approach in which two airy functions were used to calculate tangential stress, the results for which differed slightly between the square and rectangular cross-sections. Finally, the finite element analysis was conducted by using ANSYS to analyze rectangular, square, and circular 3D curved beams. In that case, all cross-sections showed similar results to the SOM approach. This study represented a unique comparison of a curved beam's tangential stress, by comparing different sources found in various studies and articles.

Introduction

There is a wide range of applications of curved beams, for example, to manufacture a small device and manufacturing of an aircraft. That type of beam is more efficient in transferring loads than straight beams. This transfer in the curved beam is affected by bending, shear, and membrane action (Mathiyazhagan & Vasiraja, 2013). In this study, the authors compared tangential stress by using the strength of materials (SOM) analysis, elasticity analysis (EA), and finite element analysis (FEA) of the curved beam of various sections. The development of the beam and bending relations should have the same cross-section throughout the beam's length. However, the varying cross-section can be caused when considering the curved beam's practical use (Subramani, Subramani, & Prasath, 2014). Figures 1 and 2 show the 2D and 3D curved beams, respectively, where a is the inner radius, b is the outer radius, and o is the circular center. The moment was applied from both ends, symmetry analysis was considered by keeping the mid-plane

fixed. For all approaches of calculation and analysis, the beam's cross-section outer radius was three times the inner radius.

Figure 1. 2D Schematic view of a curved beam.

Figure 2. 3D Rendering of a curved beam.

Literature Review

Beam elements have played a vital role in modeling mechanical engineering structures, but curved beams are more efficient in transferring loads than straight beams (Mathiyazhagan & Vasiraja, 2013). Wang and Liu described a solution for curved beams with the airy stress function method (2013). In that article, two airy stress functions were presented for elasticity analysis (EA). Another study determined the stress component by EA (Kılıç, & Aktaş, 2002). Chavan and Zhou (2016) presented a stress calculation for slender curved beams and simulated curved beam stresses (Chavan, & Zhou, 2016). Yet another study used FEM to analyze a curved cantilever beam's static and dynamic analysis with different cross-sections and different curvature types by varying load and direction (Mathiyazhagan & Vasiraja, 2013).

Other research described the FE analysis of non-linear and linear elastic beams, while considering the shear deformation, and derived a new formulation for the linear beam and discussed the theory of Reissner for non-linear beams (Ibrahimogović, & Frey, 1993). Bağcı (1991) showed the exact elasticity solutions of curved beams for stresses and deflections and developed the expression of tangential, radial stresses for different conditions, moment, force, and combined loading for different cross-sections exponentially varying trapezoidal and T-sections. As the high-rise building increases, due to the increasing population, curved beams are becoming popular for different construction projects, including highway crossing, metrorail, the bridge on the big river, etc. Subramani et al. did the FE analysis for the composite concrete structure (2014). Lin and Lin (2011) used the Lagrangian and Eulerian to derive the finite deformation analysis, while taking into consideration the deformed curvature radius under static loading and presented analytical solutions of the circular beam compared the results of ANSYS analysis.

Curved beams also have been used for energy harvesting. Nahid Hasid researched a THUNDER, which is a curved piezoelectric energy generator by finite element methods (Hasan, 2018). Curved beams have vast application areas, due to some unique advantages. One of which is the characteristic of keeping the elastic property while deformed to specific values. Tennis rackets, the arms of a robot, and stiffeners in aircraft parts are the examples of this kind of curved beam. A study presented the analytical solution of laminated curved beams and compared the finite element analysis with the ANSYS (Lin & Lin, 2011). The curved beam has also been made of a composite material, as used in aircraft manufacturing. Ismail (2014) assessed layered composite material curved beams in theoretical and experimental methodologies by computing the maximum stress and deflection of layer by layer and detecting the effect of curvature radius and shape of the curve of twelve cases.

Methods

For this current study, one specific material was used for calculation and analysis. Table 1 shows the material and chemical composition of structural steels (ASTM International, 2019); Calderón, Bohórquez, Rojas, & Pertuz, 2021). For the SOM analysis, three types of curved beams were considered in calculating the ratio of tangential stress, square, rectangular, and circular. The authors assumed that the outer radius was three times the inner radius. Tangential or circumferential stress (σ_θ) in a curved beam can be written as Equation 1 (Boresi, Schmidt, & Sidebottom, 1985):

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{N}{A} + \frac{M_o(A - rA_m)}{A_r(RA_m - A)} \quad (1)$$

where,

N = normal traction

M_o = applied moment

R = the distance from the center of curvature of the curved beam to the centroid of the beam cross-section

r = location of the element

A = the cross-sectional area of the curved beam

$A_m = \int \frac{dA}{r}$ represents dimensions of length

Table 1. Material and chemical composition of structural steels.

Property		Value	Unit		
Density		7850.00	Kg m ⁻³		
Tensile Yield Strength		250.00	MPa		
Compressive Yield Strength		250.00	MPa		
Tensile Ultimate Strength		460.00	MPa		
Compressive Ultimate Strength		0.00	Pa		
Chemical Composition (% , ≤)					
C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cu
0.26	0.40	-	0.04	0.05	0.20

Assuming, $N = 0$, tangential stress can be written as Equation 2:

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{M_o(A - rA_m)}{A_r(RA_m - A)} \quad (2)$$

Assuming that b is the outer radius and a is the inner radius, A , R , and A_m can be written as follows (Boresi et al., 1985):

$$A = (b-a)(b+a)$$

$$R = (a+b)/2$$

$$A_m = (b-a) \ln(b/a)$$

Now, from Equation 2, tangential stress can be written as Equation 3:

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{M_o \left((b-a)^2 - r \left((b-a) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right) \right)}{(b-a)^2 r \left(\left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) (b-a) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) - (b-a)^2 \right)}$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{M_o \left(b-a-r \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right)}{(b-a)^2 r \left(\left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) - b+a \right)} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{M_o(2a - r \ln 3)}{4a^2 r (2a \ln 3 - 2a)} \quad (\text{when } b = 3a)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{M_o(2a - r \ln 3)}{8a^3 r (\ln 3 - 1)}$$

When $r = a$, Equation 3 can be written as Equation 4:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - a \ln 3)}{8a^3 a (\ln 3 - 1)} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2 - \ln 3)}{8a^3 (\ln 3 - 1)}$$

When $r = b = 3a$, Equation 3 can be written as Equation 5:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - 3a \ln 3)}{8a^3 3a (\ln 3 - 1)} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2 - 3 \ln 3)}{24a^3 (\ln 3 - 1)}$$

The ratio of the tangential stress at $r = b$ and $r = a$ is defined as γ in Equation 6:

$$\gamma = \frac{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=b}}{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=a}}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\frac{M_o(2 - 3 \ln 3)}{24a^3 (\ln 3 - 1)}}{\frac{M_o(2 - \ln 3)}{8a^3 (\ln 3 - 1)}} \quad (\text{from Equations 4 \& 5}) \quad (6)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{2 - 3 \ln 3}{6 - 3 \ln 3}$$

$$\gamma = (-)0.479$$

For rectangular cross-sections, A, R, and A_m were different. Given that the width of the rectangular cross-section was double the height, the height was parallel to the calculation axis, and the height of the rectangular cross-section was half of the width (Boresi et al., 1985):

$$A = 0.5(b-a)(b-a)$$

$$R = (a+b)/2 = (3b+b)/2b$$

$$A_m = 0.5(b-a) \ln(b/a)$$

Now, from Equation 2, stress can be derived as Equation 7. When $r = a$, Equation 7 can be written as Equation 8. When $r = b = 3a$, Equation 7 can be written as Equation 9. The ratio of the tangential stress at $r = b$ and $r = a$ is defined as γ in Equation 10. For circular cross-sections, A, R, and A_m can be written as follows, where a is equal to b (Boresi et al., 1985).

$$R = 2a$$

$$A = \pi a^2$$

$$A_m = 2\pi \left(2a - \sqrt{(4a^2 - a^2)} \right) = 2\pi a(2 - \sqrt{3})$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(A - rA_m)}{Ar(RA_m - A)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o \left(0.5(b-a)^2 - r \left(0.5(b-a) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right) \right)}{0.5(b-a)^2 r \left(\left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) 0.5(b-a) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) - 0.5(b-a)^2 \right)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o \left(b-a-r \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right)}{0.5(b-a)^2 r \left(\left(\frac{a+b}{4} \right) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) - b+a \right)} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - r \ln 3)}{2a^2 r (a \ln 3 - 2a)} \quad (\text{when } b = 3a)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - r \ln 3)}{2a^3 r (\ln 3 - 2)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - a \ln 3)}{2a^3 a (\ln 3 - 2)} = \frac{M_o(2 - \ln 3)}{2a^3 (\ln 3 - 2)} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(2a - 3a \ln 3)}{2a^3 3a (\ln 3 - 1)} = \frac{M_o(2 - 3 \ln 3)}{6a^3 (\ln 3 - 2)} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=b}}{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=a}}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\frac{M_o(2 - 3 \ln 3)}{6a^3 (\ln 3 - 2)}}{\frac{M_o(2 - \ln 3)}{2a^3 (\ln 3 - 2)}} \quad (\text{from Equations 8 \& 9}) \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{2 - 3 \ln 3}{6 - 3 \ln 3}$$

$$\gamma = (-)0.479$$

Now, from Equation 2, stress can be derived as Equation 11:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(A - rA_m)}{Ar(RA_m - A)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(\pi a^2 - r2\pi a(2 - \sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^2 r(2a - 2\pi a(2 - \sqrt{3}) - \pi a^2)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(\pi a - r2\pi(2 - \sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^2 r(2a - 2\pi(2 - \sqrt{3}) - \pi a)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(a - r2(2 - \sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^2 r(2a - 2(2 - \sqrt{3}) - a)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(a - r(4 - 2\sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^2 r(a(8 - 4\sqrt{3}) - a)}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(a - r(4 - 2\sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^3 r(7 - 4\sqrt{3})}$$

When $r = a$, Equation 11 can be derived as Equation 12:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(a - a(4 - 2\sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^3 a(7 - 4\sqrt{3})} = \frac{M_o(-3 + 2\sqrt{3})}{\pi a^3(7 - 4\sqrt{3})} \quad (12)$$

When $r = b = 3a$, from Equation 11, tangential stress can be derived as Equation 13:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(a - 3a(4 - 2\sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^3 3a(7 - 4\sqrt{3})}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(1 - 3(4 - 2\sqrt{3}))}{\pi a^3 3(7 - 4\sqrt{3})}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(1 - 12 + 6\sqrt{3})}{\pi a^3(21 - 12\sqrt{3})}$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{M_o(-11 + 6\sqrt{3})}{\pi a^3(21 - 12\sqrt{3})}$$

$$(11) \quad \gamma = (-)0.436$$

The ratio of the tangential stress at $r = b$ and $r = a$ is defined as γ in Equation 14:

$$\gamma = \frac{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=b}}{(\sigma_{\theta})_{r=a}}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{M_o(-11 + 6\sqrt{3})}{\pi a^3(21 - 12\sqrt{3})} / \frac{M_o(-3 + 2\sqrt{3})}{\pi a^3(7 - 4\sqrt{3})} \quad (\text{from Equations 12 \& 13})$$

$$(14)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{(-11 + 6\sqrt{3})(7 - 4\sqrt{3})}{(21 - 12\sqrt{3})(-3 + 2\sqrt{3})}$$

Elasticity Analysis

For the elasticity analysis, two airy functions were taken in order to calculate the tangential ratio.

Function 1:

Assume a solution to the biharmonic equation,

$$\nabla^4 \Phi = \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \Phi = 0$$

where, Φ is an airy function, as in Equation 15 (Den Hartog, 1987):

$$\Phi = (a_1 r^3 + a_2 r + a_3 r \log_e r + a_4 r^{-1} + a_{24}) \sin \theta \quad (15)$$

Assuming $a_{24} = 0$, Equation 15 can be written as Equation 16:

$$\Phi = (a_1 r^3 \sin \theta + a_2 r \sin \theta + a_3 r \log_e r \sin \theta + a_4 r^{-1} \sin \theta) \quad (16)$$

Now, radial (σ_r), tangential (σ_{θ}), and shear stress ($\sigma_{r\theta}$), can be written as Equations 17-19:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \theta^2} \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial r^2} \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = \frac{-1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta} \quad (19)$$

Using MATLAB and putting the value of Φ from Equation 16 into Equations 17-19, radial, tangential, and shear stress can be written as Equations 20-22:

$$\sigma_r = \sin(\theta)(2a_1r^4 + a_3r^2 - 2a_4)/r^3$$

$$\sigma_r = \sin(\theta)(2a_1r + a_3/r - 2a_4/r^3) \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \sin(\theta)(6a_1r + a_3/r + 2a_4/r^3) \quad (21)$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = \cos(\theta)(2a_1r + a_3/r - 2a_4/r^3) \quad (22)$$

the boundary conditions for which are,

$$\sigma_r(a, \theta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(a, \theta) = 0$$

$$\sigma_r(b, \theta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(b, \theta) = 0$$

Applying the boundary conditions from Equations 20 and 22, and given that $\sin(\theta)$ and $\cos(\theta)$ cannot be zero, where θ (degrees) is the angle, the ratio of a_3 and a_1 can be derived as Equations 23 and 24:

When $r = a$,

$$2a_1a + a_3/a - 2a_4/a^3 = 0$$

$$2a + a_3/a_1a - 2a_4/a_1a^3 = 0$$

$$a_3/a_1 = 2a_4/a_1a^2 - 2a^2 \quad (23)$$

When $r = b$,

$$2a_1b + a_3/b - 2a_4/b^3 = 0$$

$$2b + a_3/a_1b - 2a_4/a_1b^3 = 0$$

$$a_4/a_1 = -a^2b^2 \quad (\text{from Equation 23})$$

$$a_3/a_1 = -2a^2 - 2b^2 \quad (24)$$

From Equation 21, tangential stress can be written as Equations 25-27:

$$\sigma_\theta = \sin(\theta)(6a_1r + a_3/r + 2a_4/r^3) \quad (25)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = 2a_1 \sin \theta \left(3r - \frac{a^2 + b^2}{r} - \frac{a^2b^2}{r^3} \right)$$

When $r = a$ ($b = 3a$ and using the values of a_4 and a_3),

$$(\sigma_\theta)_{r=a} = 2a_1 \sin \theta \left(3a - \frac{a^2 + 9a^2}{a} - \frac{9a^2a^2}{a^3} \right) \quad (26)$$

When $r = b$, ($b = 3a$ and using the values of a_4 and a_3),

$$(\sigma_\theta)_{r=b} = 2a_1 \sin \theta \left(9a - \frac{a^2 + 9a^2}{3a} - \frac{9a^2a^2}{27a^3} \right) \quad (27)$$

The ratio of the tangential stress at $r = b$ and $r = a$ is defined as γ in Equation 28:

$$\gamma = \frac{(\sigma_\theta)_{r=b}}{(\sigma_\theta)_{r=a}}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\left(9a - \frac{a^2 + 9a^2}{3a} - \frac{9a^2a^2}{27a^3} \right)}{\left(3a - \frac{a^2 + 9a^2}{a} - \frac{9a^2a^2}{a^3} \right)} \quad (\text{from Equations 26 \& 27}) \quad (28)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\left(\frac{16a}{3} \right)}{-16a}$$

$$\gamma = (-)0.330$$

Function 2:

In this case, the airy function is given as shown in Equation 29 (Budynas, 1977:

$$\Phi = (c_1 + c_2 \ln r + c_3 r^2 + c_4 r^2 \ln r) \quad (29)$$

Using MATLAB and inserting the value of Φ into Equations 17-19, radial, tangential, and shear stress can be written as Equations 30-32, respectively:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{c_2}{r^2} + 2c_3 + 2c_4 \ln r + c_4 \quad (30)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = -\frac{c_2}{r^2} + 2c_3 + 2c_4 \ln r + 3c_4 \quad (31)$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = 0 \quad (32)$$

the boundary conditions for which are,

$$\sigma_r(a, \theta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(a, \theta) = 0$$

$$\sigma_r(b, \theta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(b, \theta) = 0$$

Applying these boundary conditions into Equations 30 and 31, coefficients c_2 and c_3 can be written as follows:

$$c_2 = \frac{c_4 \{2a^2 b^2 \ln(b/a)\}}{(b^2 - a^2)}$$

$$c_3 = \frac{c_4 \{a^2(1+2\ln a) - b^2(1+2\ln b)\}}{2(b^2 - a^2)}$$

Now, from Equation 31, and using these two coefficients, the ratio of the tangential stress at $r=b$ and $r=a$ is defined as γ can be derived as Equation 33:

$$\gamma = \frac{\sigma_{\theta,(r=b)}}{\sigma_{\theta,(r=a)}}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{(-2a^2 \ln b + 2a^2 \ln a - a^2 + b^2)}{(-2b^2 \ln b + 2b^2 \ln a - a^2 + b^2)} \quad [\text{as } b = 3a]$$

$$\gamma = \frac{(-2a^2 \ln(3a) + 2a^2 \ln a - a^2 + 9a^2)}{(-18a^2 \ln(3a) + 18a^2 \ln a - a^2 + 9a^2)} \quad (33)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{(-\ln(3a) + \ln a + 4)}{(-9\ln(3a) + 9\ln a + 4)}$$

$$\gamma = (-)0.490$$

Numerical Analysis

A solid model was created with the Design Modeler of ANSYS to analyze the curved beam numerically then meshed and analyzed in ANSYS Mechanical as an application of ANSYS Workbench (Chavan, & Zhou, 2016). Figures 3-5 show the rectangular, square, and circular cross-section mesh models, respectively. FE analysis results of the rectangular, square, and circular cross-section can be visualized from Figures 6-8, respectively. As the moments were the same from both ends, symmetry analysis was considered by keeping the mid-plane fixed. Meshed and analysis were done for all cases and cross-sections in ANSYS Mechanical Workbench.

Results and Discussion

Tangential stresses were calculated at $r=a$ and $r=b$. Figure 1 shows the definitions of radii a and b . Table 2 shows the results of the ratio of tangential stress at $r=b$ and tangential stress at $r=a$, defined as γ in Equations 6, 10, 14,

28, and 33. The elasticity approach results were slightly different for the curved beam with a square cross-section than for the SOM and FE analyses. In this current study, the authors took two airy functions from the other resources, so the results may vary slightly depending on the airy function. For the rectangular cross-section, the tangential stress ratios were -0.479, -0.490, and -0.426, respectively, for the SOM, EA, and FE analyses. However, the results for the SOM and FE showed only minor differences for all types of cross-sections.

Figure 3. Mesh model of the rectangular cross-section.

Figure 4. Mesh model of the square cross-section.

Figure 5. Mesh model of the circular cross-section.

Figure 6. FE analysis results (rectangular).

Figure 7. FE analysis results (square).

Figure 8. FE analysis results (circular).

Table 2. Comparison of the results.

Cross-section of the curved beams	γ , SOM approach	γ , elasticity approach	γ , FE analysis
Square	-0.479	Function-1 (-0.330)	-0.438
Rectangular	-0.479	Function-2 (-0.490)	-0.426
Circular	-0.436		-0.428

Conclusions

In this study, the authors compared three ways of calculating the inner and outer surface tangential stress ratios using SOM, EA, and FEA. SOM showed a similar ratio, irrespective of the cross-section, validated by the ANSYS numerical analysis, which showed roughly the same ratio for all the cross-sections—rectangular, square, and circular. However, the EA approach differed slightly for the square cross-section, as it depended on the airy function (Equations 15 and 29). In conclusion, the study showed that the ratio of the tangential stress was similar among approaches and irrespective of the cross-sections of the curved beams. Part of this research was presented at a conference as a poster. As for the material chosen, only one material was considered. In the future, the tangential stress ratio comparison will be compared with new machine learning and image processing (Garfo, Mukhtadir, & Yi, 2020; Mukhtadir & Yi, 2021). Also, studies will be done by varying the cross-sections, increasing the inner and outer radius ratios, and increasing the number of mesh for the FE analysis.

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